

Innovation Requirements for Good Governance of Local Government in Urban Government of Vietnam

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Abstract: Local governance is a quite popular term, however urban local governance is one of the new governance terms in Vietnam. Currently, in the world's urbanization trend associated with building e-government, digital transformation, building smart cities, etc., the issue of good management and administration of urban governments is increasing. is a requirement. Within the scope of this article, the author introduces the most common features of urban government, the distinction between urban government and rural government; At the same time, it points out the requirements for building an urban government that meets lean requirements and operates effectively and efficiently in Vietnam.

Keywords: Local governance, urban government, Vietnam

1. INTRODUCTION

Building, inventing, and consolidating the local government organizational model is one of the most critical challenges for the cause of innovation, improvement, and the efficacy and efficiency of the legal State's activities in support of socialist rights in Vietnam. The 2013 Constitution clearly states that "local authorities are organized in administrative units of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam," and "local authorities include people's councils and people's committees organized in accordance with the characteristics of rural and urban areas," as well as islands and special administrative-economic units prescribed by law. In 2015, the 13th National Assembly, 9th session, enacted the Law on Local Government Organization, which concretized the 2013 Constitution and implemented the Party's ideas on local government. The 12th National Congress affirmed that in order to further enhance local government in our nation in the new era, "clearly defining the authority and state management responsibilities of each level of local government according to the provisions of the Constitution and law, on the basis of ensuring the unity, smoothness, effectiveness and efficiency of national administrative system." The Fatherland Front and other socio-political groups at all levels are innovative in their structure and mode of operation, and this innovation is inextricably related to the advancement of local governments' roles, responsibilities, and organizational framework. Complete the local government organization model in compliance with the legal requirements for administrative-economic special units, islands, rural, and urban areas.

In recent years, the nation's development process has encouraged urbanization nationwide. From 2000 to the present, Vietnam's urban regions have had an annual growth rate of 2.8%, indicating an acceleration of the country's urbanization process. The country's urban areas are expected to accommodate an additional 1 to 1.3 million people yearly, representing an annual growth rate of 3%. Vietnam is among the Southeast Asian nations experiencing the fastest rate of urbanization. With 888 urban areas, the national urbanization rate as of September 2022 was approximately 41.5%. These cities have made and will continue to make significant contributions to the growth of every community across the nation. The 2015 Local Government Law mandates that urban regions be handled by the government using an urban model, distinct from rural authorities, in order to foster urban development. However, many communities are still unsure about how to construct urban government models (CQĐT). In order to accomplish the aim, it is imperative that all levels of government in Vietnam conduct research on the innovative requirements for local governance in urban governments and put that research into practice right away. swift and long-term national development in the new era.

2. LOCAL GOVERNMENT AND LOCAL GOVERNMENT IN URBAN VIETNAM

* Local government

The term local government is understood in many different ways. If understood according to the general explanation of "Government" as the authors of the Vietnamese Dictionary, "Local government" includes all state agencies organized locally to control and manage. manage state affairs locally.

According to author Thai Vinh Thang and co-authors of the Ministerial-level research project "Theoretical and practical basis of innovating the organization and operations of local People's Councils":

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Local government in our country is an integral part of the people's unified state government, including local state power agencies, representing local people, led by local people. directly elected (People's Council) and other agencies and organizations established on the basis of these representative agencies and state power in accordance with the provisions of the Constitution and law (People's Committee, specialized agencies under the People's Committee). People's Committee, Standing Committee of the People's Council, committees of the People's Council,...) to manage all areas of local social life, on the basis of the principle of democratic centralism and combining the interests of local people with the interests of local people. common interest of the whole country.

Currently, officially, local government is recognized in Chapter IX of the 2013 Constitution. Accordingly, "local government is organized in administrative units of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam", "local government level includes People's Councils and People's Committees are organized in accordance with the characteristics of rural areas, urban areas, islands, and special administrative-economic units as prescribed by law" (Article 111) and in Article 110 it is stipulated:

1. The administrative units of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam are classified as follows: The country is divided into provinces and centrally run cities; The province is divided into districts, towns and provincial cities; Centrally run cities are divided into districts, towns and equivalent administrative units; Districts are divided into communes and towns; Provincial towns and cities are divided into wards and communes; The district is divided into wards. Special administrative-economic unit established by the National Assembly. 2. The establishment, dissolution, merger, division, and adjustment of administrative unit boundaries must consult local people and follow the order and procedures prescribed by law.

To concretize the provisions of the 2013 Constitution, on June 19, 2015, at the 9th session, the 13th National Assembly passed the Law on Organization of Local Governments 2015 on "Urban Local Governments" or "Urban Governments"; and on December 16, 2019, the National Assembly Office issued Consolidated Document No. 22/VBHN-VPQH consolidating the Law on Organization of Local Authorities as follows:

- Administrative units are classified: Hanoi City and Ho Chi Minh City are special provincial administrative units; The remaining provincial administrative units are classified into three types: type I, type II and type III (Point a, Clause 3, Article 3);

- "Urban authorities" or "urban local authorities" of provincial urban areas in Vietnam have been specifically promulgated by the state in regulations:

+ Local authorities in centrally run cities are the level of local authorities including the People's Council of centrally run cities and People's Committees of centrally run cities (Article 37, Chapter III Local governments in urban areas);

+ The local authority in the district is the local authority level, except in specific cases that the National Assembly stipulates that it is not the local authority level. The local government level in the district includes the People's Council and People's Committee (Article 44);

+ Local authorities in towns, provincial cities, and cities under centrally run cities are the level of local authorities including the People's Councils of towns, provincial cities, cities under centrally run cities and the People's Committees of towns and cities. belonging to a province or city belonging to a centrally run city. (Article 51).

+ The local authority in the ward is the local authority level, except in specific cases that the National Assembly stipulates that it is not the local authority level. The local government level in a ward includes the People's Council and Ward People's Committee (Article 58).

+ The local authority in the town is the local authority level, including the town People's Council and the town People's Committee (Article 65).

Thus, according to the 2013 Constitution, the current local government includes: People's Council and People's Committee, organized at three (03) levels of administrative units: provincial level, district level and commune level. Local authorities do not include inspection and adjudication agencies, which are agencies that exercise independent judicial power located locally.

* Urban local government or urban government

The term "Urban Government" is a concept arising from the concept of "Local Government". In the Law on Organization of Local Authorities in 2015, a separate chapter was issued on "Local Local Authorities in Urban Areas", this is also the "Urban Government". This Law stipulates the tasks, powers and organizational structure of Local Authorities in urban areas. centrally run cities (provincial level); districts, towns, provincial cities, centrally run cities (district level); wards and towns (ward level). However, currently there is still no state legal document that defines the concept of "Urban Government" in Vietnam, what institutions, relationships and specific operating mechanisms of these agencies include. constituent parts.

In Article 4, Law on Organization of Local Authorities 2015 and Consolidated Document No. 22/VBHN-VPQH dated December 16, 2019 stipulate:

1. Local authorities are organized in administrative units of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam specified in Article 2 of this Law in accordance with the characteristics of rural, urban, island and administrative-economic units. special economic conditions" and "(...) Local authorities in urban areas include local authorities in centrally run cities, districts, towns, provincial cities, centrally run cities, wards and towns.

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From the contents "Local government in urban areas" or "Urban government" in the Law on Organization of Local Authorities 2015 and Consolidated Document No. 22/VBHNVPQH dated December 16, 2019, the thesis overview and concept " Municipality" as follows:

- "Urban government in centrally run cities" or "Urban government at provincial level" is the level of local government including: People's Council of centrally run cities and People's Committee of centrally run cities (provincial level);
- "Urban government at the district level" or "Urban government at the district level" is the level of local government including the district People's Council and district People's Committee; "Urban government in towns, provincial cities, cities under centrally run cities" or "Urban government at district level" is the level of local authorities including the People's Councils of towns, provincial cities, and municipalities. belonging to centrally run cities and People's Committees of towns, provincial cities, and centrally run cities;
- "Urban government at ward and town level" or "Urban government at ward level" is the local government level including the People's Council of ward and town and the People's Committee of ward/town. Current local authorities in urban areas include People's Councils and People's Committees, organized at three levels of administrative units: province, district and commune. Local authorities in urban areas do not include procuracy and adjudication agencies, which are agencies that exercise independent judicial power located locally.

From the above analysis, it can be understood that urban government is a form of local government in urban areas that performs state management functions in centrally run cities; districts, towns, and cities within the province; cities belonging to centrally run cities; ward, town.

According to Dr. Vo Tri Hao - Faculty of Economic Law, Ho Chi Minh City University of Economics, "Urban government is a term to refer to a model of local government established in urban areas, used to distinguish it from the model of agricultural government." village. Urban governments often have two distinct characteristics compared to rural governments. Firstly, it is organized to shorten some levels of government, but still ensure that the distance "people - government" is not too far in space. Second, the head of the Urban Government is directly elected by the people, or in other words the government apparatus is organized according to the mayor model, requiring the head of the government to be more accountable to the people, and also has can be directly removed from office by the vote of the people.

In some countries around the world, the Urban Authority is the local authority in an urban area of that country. Depending on the division of administrative units of a country and the scale and characteristics of the urban area, the urban government can be the urban government - national (Singapore), urban government - capital, urban government. urban authority - state capital, urban authority - centrally run city, urban authority - state city, urban authority - city, provincial town,...

On the basis of research and understanding of experience in organizing government in urban areas in Vietnam through periods and organizing activities of a number of cities in the world, it is possible to give a general concept of urban government. Urban government in Vietnam is as follows: Urban government in Vietnam is the apparatus that controls and manages the work of the State in urban areas in centrally run cities/districts, towns, provincial cities, and cities. belonging to centrally run cities/wards and towns including state power agencies (People's Councils at all levels) at the local level, executive and administrative agencies (People's Committees at all levels) at the local level, along with a system of local authorities. affiliated administrative level.

Thus, "Urban government" is a specific form of local authority, organized in accordance with the characteristics of political, economic, cultural, social life, and natural conditions of the urban area in order to manages urban areas and has all the basic characteristics of a local government. The urban government not only demonstrates the general issues of local authorities in terms of the nature, position, role, representative function of the people and the relationships between governments at all levels according to the provisions of law, but also demonstrates the specific requirements of urban organization, management and development methods.

3. LEGAL REGULATIONS ON URBAN GOVERNMENT IN VIETNAM TODAY

Firstly, about the organizational structure

The implementation of the urban government model is regulated in laws of the National Assembly and Government resolutions issued in urban areas. The urban government model of each locality is specified in the Law on Organization of Local Government. Some regulations on decentralization are inadequate due to conflicts with regulations in the Construction Law, Investment Law, Bidding Law, Urban Planning Law, Civil Status Law... Model of organization of local authorities in urban areas Vietnam currently has two major limitations: First of all, urban governments are organized according to an administrative level model similar to local governments in rural areas, including 3 levels: level 1 (equivalent to a province) is a centrally run city. care; Level 2 (equivalent to district) is the district, provincial city, town and city under the city; Level 3 (equivalent to commune) is ward and town. Besides, from the organizational structure to the tasks and powers of local agencies at all levels in urban areas, the differences are not significant, proven through three contents: organizational structure of local agencies; tasks and powers of the investigation agency; The decentralization policy for urban authorities is basically the same as that of rural governments, so there are certain inadequacies in managing the activities of urban areas.

Second, about the functions and tasks of the City/Town People's Committee and Ward/Town People's Committee.

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Currently, the functions and tasks of the People's Committee of a city or town and the People's Committee of a ward or town are mainly regulated in the direction of transfer from lower-level People's Councils or People's Councils of the same level, according to the provisions of the Law on Organization of Local Government. methods to ensure organization and operations take place normally. However, some functions and tasks of the City or Town People's Committee, Ward or Town People's Committee still overlap in the vertical management of specialized agencies. At the same time, the organizational structure of specialized agencies under the People's Committee of the city or town is the same as other district-level administrative units, causing a situation where many tasks of the city/town government must be resolved. decided at the People's Committee to ensure convenience, but falls under the authority of departments and other departments.

Regarding decentralization policy for local authorities in urban areas: After the Law on Organization of Local Authorities in 2015 was promulgated, the issuance of documents on decentralization of management for local authorities was carried out by the Government. The most notable among them is Resolution No. 21/NQ-CP/2016 on decentralization of state management between the Government and the People's Committees of provinces and centrally run cities; between the Provincial People's Committee and the People's Committee of cities and towns of the province. However, the promulgation of these urban-oriented regulations has encountered some limitations. Specifically, the documents mentioned are basically just the inheritance of documents related to decentralization to the Investor Authority in the past without adjusting or enhancing the content; These special mechanisms continue to focus on managing large cities, which are centrally run cities, without taking into account other small and medium-sized urban areas such as provincial cities, towns or townships. Thus, although they are urban areas, only special type and type 1 urban areas - corresponding territorial administrative units that are centrally run cities - enjoy special regulations, the remaining urban areas still apply the same regulations. The general mechanism has no scientific basis; There is no specific, outstanding document for urban areas in the provinces such as Decree No. 48/2017/ND-CP on specific financial mechanisms and policies for the city. Ho Chi Minh City, so urban areas do not have high autonomy in their activities.

4. DISTINGUISH BETWEEN URBAN GOVERNMENT AND RURAL GOVERNMENT

In terms of overall research on rural society, we can point out the basic characteristics of rural areas that can be easily distinguished from urban areas, including:

- Economically: rural areas must be closely linked to a traditional social labor profession, characterized and highlighted by agricultural production activities, creating a professional connection between rural people and the land.
- Regarding population: includes residential areas that are often small in number and small in area within the administrative area. Village relations, village conventions, and village rules play a big role.
- Culturally: strong village relationships, often based on blood and clan relationships; community cohesion, social behavior heavy on customary laws and rituals.

In Vietnam today, the distinction between rural and urban areas is still not clear, because rural and urban areas are still intertwined and intertwined, in rural areas there are urban areas and in urban areas there are rural areas. For example, Hanoi city is a special urban area, but has 58.1% of the population in rural areas. Hai Phong city is a class 1 urban area but up to 2/3 of the area is rural, only 1/3 of the area is urban.

The city is seen as a whole that cannot be divided into separate parts, an inseparable connection and collection. The socio-economic infrastructure system is a single organization, each part of which is closely interconnected throughout the entire urban area to meet the needs of economic development and people's lives. people. The population in the city is completely organized, not divided into separate blocks; they may live in one area but work in another. On the contrary, the urban population is formed from different origins, from different regions and has an independent life with an integrated lifestyle; always changing and rarely linked by lineage, tradition or social rules; while in rural areas, legal standards and community rules are valued. Urban areas are also political - administrative centers, economic centers, cultural, sports, educational, scientific and technological centers of the whole country, a region, a province or a district. With the above characteristics of urban areas, the contents and forms of organizing and implementing state management in urban areas also have different characteristics from those in rural areas. State management in urban areas must be focused and unified, ensuring smoothness, speed and efficiency. An urban area should only have a unified management apparatus; subordinate units are only extensions of the urban government.

The history of local government shows that, from the early days of establishing the Democratic Republic of Vietnam, urban government and rural government were regulated in two separate documents with different organizational models. Decree No. 63-SL dated November 22, 1945 of the Chairman of the Provisional Government of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam on the organization and operation of the People's Councils and Administrative Committees at all levels, accordingly, the government Power is organized into three levels, of which there are two complete levels of government, the provincial and commune levels, with both the People's Council and the administrative committee, while at the district level there is only the administrative committee because it is considered the highest level. intermediate.

Decree No. 77 dated December 21, 1945 of the President of the Provisional Government of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam on the organization of the people's government in towns and cities, according to which the government is organized into two levels, Only the city level has a complete government, that is, both the People's Council and the Administrative Committee, while the

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neighborhood level only has an administrative committee without the People's Council. This regulation is completely reasonable because in cities and urban areas, the river population is concentrated and cannot be divided like a province into districts.

The 2013 Constitution re-implemented the organization of urban government and rural government, in Clause 2, Article 111 of the 2013 Constitution stipulates: "The local government level includes the People's Council and the People's Committee, which are organized in accordance with the characteristics of rural areas, urban areas, islands, and special administrative-economic units prescribed by law.

If urban government and rural government are unified, it will create a stereotyped and rigid government apparatus that cannot distinguish the differences in power organization and state administrative management in urban areas and in the state administration. rural areas while the characteristics, properties and management requirements in each area are different. For example, the governments of cities and urban areas such as Hanoi Capital, Ho Chi Minh City, Da Nang City... are also organized similarly to other provincial governments, which is unreasonable and unresponsive. are required to manage and administer work and there is no corresponding authority in resolving other issues related to population, social security, employment... This can easily lead to a situation of "overreaching". barriers" of localities in setting out their own regulations and applications in their localities.

As for urban governments, the 2015 Law on Local Government Organization stipulates: Urban People's Councils also have the responsibility to decide on issues related to urban management such as: deciding on construction planning, and urban development within the scope of decentralization, decide on measures to manage population in the city and organize urban residential life... the People's Committee in urban areas also has the additional responsibility of organizing implementation Perform tasks related to urban management such as: implementing policies and measures to create financial resources and mobilize capital for urban development; Construction and unified management of urban infrastructure works according to the provisions of law... In addition, the tasks and powers of district and ward governments have been adjusted to suit unified management requirements. Unified and interconnected in inner city and urban areas in urban areas (focusing on implementing two groups of tasks related to deciding on local issues, including: i) Approving district and ward budgets according to regulations of the State Budget Law and ii) Electing personnel of the People's Council and People's Committee at the same level).

Thus, the tasks and powers of local governments in rural areas focus on implementing management by territory, while in urban areas they focus on implementing management by industry and field. Such regulations aim to suit the characteristics of rural and urban areas, not to be stereotyped or mechanical, to promote the role and functions of each type of government, and not to let legal regulations act as barriers. Creativity and flexible application for the purpose of developing and promoting local strengths.

5. REQUIREMENTS OF GOOD URBAN GOVERNMENT GOVERNANCE

Just like good state governance, local governance in urban areas to be effective and efficient in governance needs to meet the following basic requirements:

- *Local governance in urban areas must be associated with widespread consensus and participation in management by the people*

To gain consensus in organizations, especially in urban government governance, there need to be ways to achieve consensus through government activities to harmonize the interests of individuals and public. people and organizations as well as the state government in general, which directly benefits the urban government. Only then will governance work have high consensus and ensure the benefits of the entire community and the effectiveness and efficiency of governance.

To have high consensus, first of all, when participating in the governance process of urban government, people must have a minimum level of professional knowledge, legal knowledge, and cultural knowledge. - social and technical science and technology to grasp and understand policies and laws as well as the application of those policies and laws in the process of solving common problems in the locality. For example, when participating in work related to procedures for granting land use rights certificates, if people understand the provisions of the Land Law, they will quickly grasp the processes and procedures for granting land use rights certificates. red by any government departments on the basis of the Land Law.

To have high consensus, another point worth noting is: when promulgating local policies, decisions to apply in management or action measures, the government must eliminate factors that cause Disagreements between participating subjects such as lack of equality, discrimination between gender, ethnicity, religion or social status (especially the implementation of projects related to social security: hunger eradication) poverty, public health, climate change, gender issues are inherent problems in Vietnam...). Therefore, individual citizens, when participating with the government with a direct or indirect representative mechanism using their knowledge and understanding, can contribute their opinions on policies or advise them. government before issuing administrative decisions.

In addition, with awareness of human rights and civil rights, people can also request state management agencies and local officials and civil servants to constantly improve their management skills. to meet the rights requirements of individual citizens, especially when they require access to quality public services provided by the government.

The educational level of individual citizens is also a factor that determines whether or not they want to exercise their rights and responsibilities in local governance. Therefore, there needs to be a mechanism to encourage and create favorable conditions for these groups of people to be able to participate. For example, if there is an open and transparent bidding mechanism in accordance with international standards for road construction projects, environmental pollution treatment, and tree planting projects with State

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funding or money from other sources, of ODA aid sources, assigning the private community to implement these projects will, on the one hand, improve the efficiency of public financial management, and on the other hand, avoid the current risk of corruption and bribery.

Therefore, in local governance, it is necessary to pay attention to organizational forms and methods to mobilize widespread participation of people to consult with all sectors of society and have an informed feedback mechanism. through procedures for petitions, complaints and denunciations of public service beneficiaries.

In addition to the consensus participation in urban local governance of individual citizens, the community or social organizations located in the local area also contributes to improving the quality of policy promulgation. , prepare and implement local plans. Because, when communities and organizations with the participation of different groups in society have certain understanding of specific local conditions, the government's planning process will be highly adaptive. more practical, as well as a greater possibility of success. In addition, this participation is also the basis for creating and encouraging financial, material and labor contributions to urban local governance activities.

Community participation often forms partnerships in urban local governance from joint initiatives of governments, businesses, private economic organizations, non-profit organizations, volunteer organizations, local community associations and organizations and create opportunities for this relationship to develop through a mutual monitoring mechanism to prevent manipulation by interest groups and moreover, building trust for local actors, breaking down barriers to the government. However, this participation requires official commitment and support from Local Government Agencies.

- Requirements for rule of law in local governance

In the most general sense, the rule of law is a legal position or an institutional system where everyone must obey and respect the law, from single individuals to public agencies. The rule of law is expressed in the following aspects:

Firstly , the decisions and policies issued by the urban government need to be close to the reality, conditions and circumstances of the locality in the urban area but not contrary to central decisions.

Second , through its authority to promulgate policies and decisions, urban authorities need to create a fair and equitable legal framework and corridor and create for people the habit of living and working in framework of the law. In addition, the government needs to have a clear mechanism for checking, inspecting, and supervising the handling of common local affairs so that people can check and monitor the activities of government agencies. urban rights. For example, through voter ballots, through reporting activities to voters, through voters' recommendations on the government's management activities, people can grasp the resolution and extent of the problem. resolve common affairs according to the duties and powers of the administrative agency, from which appropriate recommendations can be made if the administrative agency does not properly perform its responsibilities according to regulations. Therefore, state governance in general and local urban governance in particular not only require adequate legal regulations but also must ensure objectivity and fairness. The implementation of the law must always emphasize the protection of human rights and civil rights, especially those belonging to disadvantaged groups or minorities in society.

- Requirements for transparency and accountability of local governments in local governance

Transparency in local governance in urban areas is reflected in two main aspects: public communication conducted by the government and citizens' rights to access information. However, both of these aspects are difficult to implement if the public communication issue is not paid attention to by the state government in the first place. For example, state authorities in general, in traditional management activities, always tend to hide and not disseminate information for the reason of keeping it secret, and then information has become a tool for actions. due to corruption and bureaucracy, the management entity has very little responsibility for its activities.

Thus, openness and transparency are one of the key principles in state governance, so local governance in urban areas is most effective when information is provided by urban authorities. must be timely and appropriate for people to easily use. At the same time, the government must not only announce and provide information about its management decisions but also disseminate and explain important decisions to people. people and the reasons for making those decisions fully. For example, decisions to recover land for use in economic activities must be clear to avoid widespread and illegal land acquisition; Decisions for foreigners to invest in domestic economic development must be based on specific conditions in each province, each region and on the general development situation of the world... Therefore, publicly, Transparency is a prerequisite to ensure that government is always truly responsible and helps improve predictability.

As for urban government accountability in governance activities, it is understood that the urban government accepts responsibility for committed actions and provides a mechanism through which this action can be monitored. , evaluate and judge.

Accountability is expressed through government reports, which is the responsibility of an individual or organization (People's Council, People's Committee or Chairman of the People's Committee, department, branch, division, etc.) to report and answer about their governance activities before elected bodies and voters answer about issues within the scope and authority of their management. In state governance in general, and local urban governance in particular, accountability is a manifestation of the people's control mechanism over state management agencies.

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Accountability includes all issues related to the responsibility of the state apparatus and those who hold and exercise state power. Accountability is expressed in two directions: Responsibility of subordinates to superiors (internal responsibility) and responsibility of the public apparatus to society (external responsibility, or downward responsibility). below).

Accordingly, the accountability of state government agencies is also analyzed from the perspective of responsibility, which is the government's public reporting of the work they undertake to other subjects (for agencies). superiors, elected bodies, the private sector, radio organizations, the public and parties related to decisions that the government issues) in accordance with the law, this is Ways to measure the performance of state government agencies. However, reporting and accountability responsibilities cannot be fulfilled without transparency and a system of complete and accurate regulations. If there is a lack of accountability, governance activities will face many internal problems such as embezzlement, abuse of public funds, authoritarianism, factionalism, group interests, and concealment of revenue and expenditure. and internal management is not public.

Therefore, implementing accountability requires attention to basic issues such as: how to be accountable to higher-level authorities, what level and responsibility; Explain how capital and public funds are used to donors for local projects; explain to beneficiaries of services (especially relief services); Internal explanations to officials and civil servants; explain to organizations and units at the same level and lower levels. The content of the explanation must be based on the duties, powers as well as the job title and position of each cadre and civil servant as prescribed by law (for example, the 2008 Law on Cadres and Civil Servants, regulations, working mode).

To improve the accountability of the state in general and urban authorities in particular in state governance activities, first, the state needs to be organized in a way that ensures real control and balance between executive, legislative and judicial authorities. The National Assembly and People's Council must become professional agencies (including full-time delegates and a team of supporting experts) and supervise all activities of state agencies other than the state. Judicial agencies (Courts, Procuracy, judgment enforcement) during their operations must ensure the principle of "independence in trial and only obey the law". In addition, these agencies need to improve transparency in their operations through supervision and criticism of elected bodies, voters, and social organizations, for example, the participation of The Fatherland Front and its member organizations and other social organizations participate in the policy-making process and monitor the accountability of local governments....

In addition, the state needs to provide a legal framework to promote citizen rights and require public agencies to be transparent, creating mechanisms for people to interact effectively with the state through increased communication. access accurate information and enhance the role of mass media agencies.

In summary, openness, transparency and accountability of local governments in local governance is both an objective requirement of the integration process, a requirement of the law enforcement process, and a mechanism to control the organization of law enforcement to ensure that state governance activities in general and local governance in particular are carried out within the framework of the law and evaluated by criteria and standards. of the law from uniformity and consistency; the assurance is clear, accurate, and easy to understand; to the reliability and predictability of the law.

- Local governance always cares about social benefits and justice

In essence, the relationship of interest in local governance in urban areas is the relationship between state agencies and competent people on the one hand and individual citizens, organizations and local social communities. This relationship originates from the requirements of production relations and economic relations transformed into the needs of social life and each member. Economic relations and interest relations can be considered the "material core" of relationships. Because benefits are the most direct step in creating motivation to satisfy the need to motivate people to participate in governance relations with local authorities. The greater the demand, the greater the attractiveness of benefits to participating parties.

Benefits are also a reflection of the needs of individuals, organizations, and communities when participating in economic relationships. Therefore, harmoniously combining and properly resolving the relationship between interests in local governance in urban areas will create motivation for local development.

Equity in local governance in urban areas means that governments at all levels need to ensure fairness in serving all different subjects in society without discrimination of class, ethnicity, religion, or status. society. The government should not create any exclusion from the participation and supervision of citizens and organizations in social governance activities. In addition, urban authorities also need to have policies and plans to encourage and create conditions to maintain the participation of all local sectors in governance activities, especially for vulnerable groups. The most vulnerable include poor groups, women, girls, and people affected by the consequences of war. On that basis, local state agencies rely on the legal system and management documents of the central agency to apply to these target groups, especially in ensuring social security. society in the fairest way possible so that every member feels entitled to benefits, is not cut off from the flow of life, and has the opportunity to improve his or her life.

6. CONCLUSION

Local governments in urban areas have a very important position and role in the political system in general, and in the state apparatus in particular, as the agency representing the will and aspirations of the People; is the place to directly plan and implement the policies and legal policies of the Party and State, taking care of all aspects of life for local people in urban areas. In order to organize good

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governance apparatus and operations of local government in urban areas in Vietnam to be carried out in a streamlined manner, ensuring democratic centralism and effective and efficient operations, it is necessary to meet the following requirements: Cua62u demands innovation in the current urban government governance process with the participation of many organizations and unions, mobilizing and promoting the intelligence, suggestions and plans of people and businesses.

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